

Preparation and study of an epoxy resin based cobalt(II) ion selective electrode using a cobalt(II) complex

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The preparation and applications of an epoxy resin membrane based Co^{II} ion selective electrode, containing diethyl phthalate (DEP) as plasticizer and impregnated with Co^{II} complex of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-benzoxypyrazole, have been described. The electrode shows stable potential response in the working range 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} M of Co^{II} with a slope of 33 mV per decade change in concentration, the response remaining constant in the pH range 3.0–6.0. Optimization of various experimental parameters, interference studies and precision and accuracy of the method have been carried out. Usefulness of the cobalt selective electrode has been demonstrated by determination of cobalt in nickel salts and in sea water.

In keeping with growing popularity of ion selective electrodes (ISEs) as tools for analysis and in continuation of our work in developing simple ISEs^{1,2}, we report here the preparation, study and applications of an epoxy resin based cobalt(II) ion selective electrode impregnated with cobalt(II) complex of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-benzoxypyrazole.

Results and Discussion

In order to prepare the ISE with best response performance, the membrane composition of the electrode was optimized. Of the various plasticizers like dibutyl phthalate (DBP), diethyl phthalate (DEP), dioctyl phthalate (DOP), tributyl phthalate (TBP), propylene glycol (PG) and glycerin (G) which were tried in varying proportions, the electrodes with only DBP and DEP gave satisfactory performance; the results of ISEs with membranes containing other plasticizers were not encouraging in terms of sensitivity. Membranes with plasticizer G were found to be sticky and could not be used further. Membranes with plasticizers were found to have better elasticity in comparison to those without plasticizers, which were found to be brittle and gave much lower values of slope in terms of mV per decade change in concentration. The optimum membrane composition (w/w) of Co^{II} selective electrode was found to be as follows : Resin Araldite[®] GY 257 (60.8%), hardner HY 837 (21.9 %), plasticizer DBP or DEP (14.6%) and carrier cobalt complex of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-benzoxypyrazole (2.7%). In order to determine the optimum concentration of the activating solution, the membranes were activated with Co^{II} solutions of concentrations in the range 0.1–2.0 M for varying length of time from 5 to 48 h. It was noted that maximum and steady potential response

was obtained when the membranes were activated with 1.0 M cobalt(II) solution for 24 h. The pH-dependance of the electrode potential was investigated over the pH range 2–12 for 10^{-2} M Co^{II} solution. It was observed that the potential response remained constant in the working pH range 3.0–6.0 for the two electrodes containing DBP and DEP as the plasticizers. Above and below these pH values, a sharp change in potential response was observed.

The ISEs prepared from membranes with two different plasticizers DBP and DEP generated stable potential response for Co^{II} solutions of varying concentrations. With the plasticizer DBP, the slope of the calibration plot of emf against Co^{II} concentration was found to be 30 mV per decade change in cobalt concentration, while with DEP, it was observed to be 33 mV per decade change in cobalt concentration. The studies with both the membrane electrodes demonstrated a linear potential response in the concentration range of 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} M.

Though both the membranes, prepared using DBP and DEP plasticizers, showed similar electrodes characteristics, the one with DEP showed somewhat better slope of 33 mV per decade change in cobalt concentration; hence the later was used for further studies and applications.

The maximum response time required to obtain a steady potential response was found to be about 60 s for the entire working range of Co^{II} concentration. The electrodes were found to be effective over a period of two months if stored properly by dipping in 0.01 M Co^{II} ion solution.

In order to investigate the selectivity of the Co^{II} selective electrode, its response was examined in the presence of various foreign ions. Potentiometric selectivity coefficients

were obtained by using fixed interference method³ at 10^{-2} M concentration of the interfering ions. The values of selectivity coefficients for ions like Na^+ , K^+ , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Te^{4+} and As^{3+} were found to be much less than unity suggesting that the electrode responses selectively to Co^{II} ion in the presence of these ions. The precision and accuracy of the cobalt determination using the proposed cobalt electrode were determined by analyzing ten test solutions containing 1×10^{-2} M cobalt concentration which gave a mean value of $9.95 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.07 \times 10^{-4}$ at 95% confidence limit.

The usefulness of cobalt selective electrode developed in the present work was demonstrated by determination of cobalt in nickel salt samples (Co in nickel nitrate = 0.0025 %, in nickel sulfate = 0.0032%). The Co^{II} ISE was also used for the determination of cobalt in samples of sea water (4 μg Co/100 ml). The results obtained were found to be in good agreement with those obtained by polarography or atomic absorption spectrometry.

Experimental

Cobalt(II) complex of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-benzoxypyrazole, the active ingredient with which the membrane was impregnated, was prepared⁴ by refluxing the reagent with cobalt(II) chloride in 2 : 1 proportion in alcohol for 1 h and then pouring on ice to obtain the solid complex. The resin Araldite[®] GY 257 and Hardner HY 837 were obtained from Ciba Speciality Chemicals (India) Ltd. A mixture of hexane : 1-butanol (4 : 1) was used as a diluent for dissolving the resin, reagent and plasticizer. The prepared membranes were attached to glass tubes using the adhesive Stick-Fast (Enelbee Co.). A stock solution (0.100 M) of Co^{II} was prepared by dissolving appropriate quantity of cobalt(II) sulfate in distilled water.

To the resin Araldite[®] GY 257 (0.25 g) and hardner HY 837 (0.09 g), the respective plasticizer DBP or DEP (0.06 g) was added and the resulting mixture was dissolved in the diluent (~2 ml). Then the cobalt complex of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-benzoxypyrazole (0.011 g), dissolved in minimum quantity of the diluent, was added to it with stirring. The resulting homogenous mixture was then poured into a low density polyethylene casting with an

inner diameter of 28 mm and was allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature. After about 48 h, a smooth membrane of approximately 0.3 mm thickness was obtained. From this master membrane, circular discs of about 10 mm each were cut out and glued with the help of Stick-Fast to one end of glass tubes (150 mm \times 10 mm) that were open at both the ends⁵. Membranes without plasticizers were also prepared and subjected to the same treatment as the ones containing plasticizers.

The following electrochemical cell assembly was used for emf measurements :

Electrical contact was established by dipping a platinum wire in the glass tube containing activated membrane in contact with 0.1 M Co^{II} ion solution (0.5 ml) that served as the internal reference solution. A standard saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as an external reference electrode. A salt-bridge with agar-agar in saturated potassium chloride was used to establish electrical contact between the solution being examined and the reference electrode. All emf measurements were made vs SCE at room temperature using an Equip-Tronics EQ-609 potentiometer having a high impedance.

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